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A

SEMINAR REPORT

ON

ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY

S.Y. B.TECH CHEMICAL ENGINEERING

By

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CERTIFICATE

This is to certify that the project entitled “ENHANCED OIL RECOVERY” has been carried out by DUSHYANT OJHA under my guidance in partial fulfilment of the degree of Bachelor of Engineering in Chemical Engineering of University of Pune during the academic year 2020-2024. To the best of my knowledge and belief this work has not been submitted elsewhere for the award of any other degree.

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List of Figures

Figure No.	Title	Page no.
1.	EOR target for different hydrocarbon	8
2.	Effect of capillary number on residual oil saturation	9
3.	Effect of mobility ratio on displaceable oil	10
4.	Classification of EOR Methods	12
5.	Cyclic Steam Stimulation (CSS)	14
6.	Steam Flooding	14
7.	Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage (SAGD)	15
8.	Tangle flags	17
9.	In situ Combustion	19
10.	THAI & CAPRI Process	20
11.	Miscible flooding (change in concentration profile)	21
12.	EOR Production Worldwide	38
13.	Current EOR production from contributing countries	39
14.	Major EOR projects & production worldwide	39

List of Tables

Table No.	Title	Page no.
1.	Classified EOR methods with functions	11
2.	Comparing some of the characteristics of the three cases	33
3.	Comparing oil production data between the three EOR cases	34
4.	Comparing water-cut and water production data between the projects	34

CONTENTS

Sr. No.	Title	Page no.
	List of Figures	4
	List of Tables	4
	Contents	5
	Abstract	6
1.	INTRODUCTION	7
1.1	IOR/EOR	8
1.2	Recovery of Residual Oil	9-10
2.	EOR METHODS	11-12
2.1	Thermal Method	13
2.1.1	Cyclic Steam Stimulation (CSS)	13
2.1.2	Steam Flooding	14
2.1.3	Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage (SAGD)	15-17
2.1.4	In situ Combustion	18-20
2.2	Non-Thermal Method	20
2.2.1	Miscible Flooding	21-23
2.2.2	Chemical Flooding	24-26
2.2.3	Other Methods	26-27
3.	CASE STUDIES	28
	• The San Andres project	28-29
	• Tupungato-Refugio project	30-31
	• Xinjaing project	32-33
	Comparison between projects	32-35
4.	EOR CHALLENGES	36
4.1	Mature Oil Fields	36
4.2	Huge Initial Capital Investment	36
4.3	Chemical Import Dependence	36-37
4.4	Oil Price Effect	37
4.5	Lack of EOR Experts	37
5.	CURRENT STATUS OF EOR	38-39
6.	CONCLUSION & REFERENCES	40-43

ABSTRACT

Recently, the Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) research and implemented projects (pilots/full field) show massive interest from all major E&P companies, especially CO₂ injection or flooding in oil reservoirs, to improve the oil recovery of the target reservoirs. Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) projects are usually applied after the secondary recovery phase. The Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) application is to recover the remaining oil, after the primary and secondary recovery phases, via enhancing the oil displacement and sweep efficiencies. The oil displacement efficiency could be improved by reducing the oil viscosity or lowering the interfacial tension. In contrast, the sweep efficiency could be improved by reducing the oil viscosity or lowering the interfacial tension. In contrast, the sweep efficiency could be improved by developing a favourable mobility ratio between the displacing fluid and the remaining oil.

Nearly 2.0×10^{12} barrels ($0.3 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3$) of conventional oil and 5.0×10^{12} barrels ($0.8 \times 10^{12} \text{ m}^3$) of heavy oil will remain in reservoirs worldwide after conventional recovery methods have been exhausted. Much of this oil would be recovered by Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) methods, which are part of the general scheme of Improved Oil Recovery (IOR). The choice of the method and the expected recovery depends on many considerations, economic as well as technological. This paper examines the EOR methods that have been tested in the field. Some of these have been commercially successful, while others are largely of academic interest.

Keywords: Enhanced oil recovery; EOR; Reservoir lithology; CO₂; Steam injection; Air injection; Chemical Flooding

CHAPTER 1

INTRODUCTION

The world will encounter a new challenge in the energy field called Enhanced Oil Recovery (EOR) technologies, where discovering hydrocarbon reservoirs will decrease, and non-renewable energy will play a key role. Therefore, increasing the recovery factors after primary and secondary production in mature reservoirs will be critical in the growing energy demand in the coming years. Many tertiary recoveries (EOR) methods are chemical flooding, gas injection, and thermal flooding. Choosing the best way to increase oil recovery factors by enhanced oil recovery methods depends on recovery parameters screening, such as rock characteristics, availability of injection material, the reservoir fluid type, available equipment, oil properties, and other items.

The current EOR technologies are presented in a proper perspective, pointing out the technical reasons for the lack of success. Methods for improving oil recovery, in particular those concerned with lowering the interstitial oil saturation, have received a great deal of attention both in the laboratory and in the field. From the vast amount of literature on the subject, one gets the impression that it is relatively simple to increase oil recovery beyond secondary (assuming that the reservoir lends itself to primary and secondary recovery). It is shown that this is not the case. Many reservoirs suitable for steam injection and carbon dioxide have already been exploited and are approaching maturity. Other EOR methods suffer from limitations that have little to do with economics. Recovering incremental oil is complex and costly, and has been successful only for a few processes under exacting conditions. Nevertheless, EOR will continue to have an important place in oil production, in view of the escalating energy demand and the tight supply. It is suggested that much research is needed to develop technologies for recovering over two-thirds of the oil that will remain unrecovered in reservoirs.

1.1 IOR v/s EOR

The terms EOR and IOR have been used loosely and interchangeably at times. IOR, or improved oil recovery, is a general term which implies improving oil recovery by any means. For example, operational strategies, such as infill drilling and horizontal wells, improve vertical and areal sweep, leading to an increase in oil recovery. Enhanced oil recovery, or EOR, is more specific in concept, and it can be considered as a subset of IOR. EOR implies a reduction in oil saturation below the residual oil saturation (S_{Or}). Recovery of oils retained due to capillary forces (after a waterflood in light oil reservoirs), and oils that are immobile or nearly immobile due to high viscosity (heavy oils and tar sands) can be achieved only by lowering the oil saturation below S_{Or} . Miscible processes, chemical floods and steam-based methods are effective in reducing residual oil saturation, and are hence EOR methods. The main focus of this paper is on EOR methods. The target of EOR varies considerably for the different types of hydrocarbons. Figure 1 shows the fluid saturations and the target of EOR for typical light and heavy oil reservoirs and tar sands. For light oil reservoirs, EOR is usually applicable after secondary recovery operations, and the EOR target is ~45% OOIP. Heavy oils and tar sands respond poorly to primary and secondary recovery methods, and the bulk of the production from such reservoirs come from EOR methods.

Fig. 1 EOR target for different hydrocarbon

1.2 RECOVERY OF RESIDUAL OIL

Mobilization of residual oil is influenced by two major factors: Capillary Number (N_c) and Mobility Ratio (M). Capillary Number is defined as $N_c = v\mu/\sigma$, where v is the Darcy velocity (m/s), μ is the displacing fluid viscosity (Pa.s) and σ is the interfacial tension (N/m). The most effective and practical way of increasing the Capillary Number is by reducing σ , which can be done by using a suitable surfactant or by the application of heat. An approximation of the effect of Capillary Number on residual oil saturation is shown in Figure 2. Capillary number at the end of a waterflood is $\sim 10^{-7}$. A 50% reduction in residual oil saturation requires that the Capillary Number be increased by 3 orders of magnitude. Capillary number in a miscible displacement becomes infinite, and under such conditions, residual oil saturation in the swept zone can be reduced to zero if the mobility ratio is “favourable”.

Fig. 2 Effect of capillary number on residual oil saturation

Mobility ratio is defined as $M = \lambda_{ing} / \lambda_{ed}$, where λ_{ing} is the mobility of the displacing fluid (e.g. water), and λ_{ed} is the mobility of the displaced fluid (oil). ($\lambda = k/\mu$, where k is the effective permeability, (m²) and μ is the viscosity (Pa.s) of the fluid concerned). Mobility ratio influences the microscopic (pore level) and macroscopic (areal and vertical sweep) displacement efficiencies. A value of $M > 1$ is considered unfavourable, because it indicates that the displacing fluid flows more readily than the displaced fluid (oil), and it can cause channelling of the displacing fluid, and as a result, bypassing of some of the residual oil. Under such conditions, and in the absence of viscous instabilities, more displacing fluid is needed to obtain a given residual oil saturation. The effect of mobility ratio on displaceable oil is shown in Figure 3, the data for which was obtained from calculations using Buckley-Leverett theory for waterflooding. The three curves represent 1, 2 and 3 pore volumes of total fluid injected, respectively. Displacement efficiency is increased when $M = 1$, and is denoted a “favourable” mobility ratio.

Fig. 3 Effect of mobility ratio on displaceable oil

CHAPTER 2

EOR METHODS

Many EOR methods have been used in the past, with varying degrees of success, for the recovery of light and heavy oils, as well as tar sands. A general classification of these methods is shown in Figure 4. Thermal methods are primarily intended for heavy oils and tar sands, although they are applicable to light oils in special cases. Non-thermal methods are normally used for light oils. Some of these methods have been tested for heavy oils, however, have had limited success in the field. Above all, reservoir geology and fluid properties determine the suitability of a process for a given reservoir. Among thermal methods, steam-based methods have been more successful commercially than others. Among non-thermal methods, miscible flooding has been remarkably successful, however applicability is limited by the availability and cost of solvents on a commercial scale. Chemical methods have generally been uneconomic in the past, but they hold promise for the future. Among immiscible gas injection methods, CO₂ floods have been relatively more successful than others for heavy oils.

EOR Method		Pressure Support	Sweep Improvement	IFT Reduction	Wettability Alteration	Viscosity Reduction	Oil Swelling	Hydrocarbon Single Phase	Compositional Change ¹	Incremental Recovery Factor
Waterflood	Waterflood									Base case ²
	Engineered water									Low
Gasflood: immiscible	Hydrocarbon									Moderate
	CO ₂									High
	Nitrogen or flue gas							3	3	Moderate
Gasflood: miscible	Hydrocarbon								4	High
	Hydrocarbon WAG								4	Very high
	CO ₂									High
	CO ₂ WAG									Highest
Thermal	Steam									High
	High-pressure air									High
Chemical	Polymer									Low
	Surfactant									Moderate
	ASP									High

IFT = interfacial tension
WAG = water-alternating-gas
ASP = alkali-surfactant-polymer

1. Change of composition of liquid hydrocarbon.
2. Waterflooding provides the base case for comparison of other methods.
3. Oil stripping occurs as miscibility develops.
4. Condensing and vaporizing exchange.

Table. 1 Classified EOR methods with functions

Fig. 4 Classification of EOR Methods

2.1 THERMAL METHOD

Thermal methods have been tested since 1950's, and they are the most advanced among EOR methods, as far as field experience and technology are concerned. They are best suited for heavy oils (10-20° API) and tar sands ($\leq 10^\circ$ API). Thermal methods supply heat to the reservoir, and vaporize some of the oil. The major mechanisms include a large reduction in viscosity, and hence mobility ratio. Other mechanisms, such as rock and fluid expansion, compaction, steam distillation and vis breaking may also be present. Thermal methods have been highly successful in Canada, USA, Venezuela, Indonesia and other countries.

2.1.1 Cyclic Steam Stimulation (CSS)

Cyclic steam stimulation is a “single well” process, and consists of three stages, as shown in Figure 5. In the initial stage, steam injection is continued for about a month. The well is then shut in for a few days for heat distribution, denoted by soak. Following that, the well is put on production. Oil rate increases quickly to a high rate, and stays at that level for a short time, and declines over several months. Cycles are repeated when the oil rate becomes uneconomic. Steam-oil ratio is initially 1-2 or lower, and it increases as the number of cycles increase. Near-wellbore geology is important in CSS for heat distribution as well as capture of the mobilized oil. CSS is particularly attractive because it has quick pay-out, however, recovery factors are low (10-40% OIP). In a variation, CSS is applied under fracture pressure. The process becomes more complex as communication develops among wells.

Fig. 5 Cyclic Steam Stimulation (CSS)

2.1.2 Steam Flooding

Steam flooding (Fig. 6) is a pattern drive, similar to water- flooding, and performance depends highly on pattern size and geology. Steam is injected continuously, and it forms a steam zone which advances slowly. Oil is mobilized due to viscosity reduction. Oil saturation in the swept zone can be as low as 10%. Typical recovery factors are in the range 50-60% OIP. Steam override and excessive heat loss can be problematic.

Fig. 6 Steam Flooding

2.1.3 Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage (SAGD)

SAGD was developed by Butler for the in situ recovery of the Alberta bitumen. The process relies on the gravity segregation of steam, utilizing a pair of parallel horizontal wells, placed 5 m apart (in the case of tar sands) in the same vertical plane. The schematic is shown in Figure 7. The top well is the steam injector, and the bottom well serves as the producer. Steam rises to the top of the formation, forming a steam chamber. High reduction in viscosity mobilizes the bitumen, which drains down by gravity and is captured by the producer placed near the bottom of the reservoir. Continuous injection of steam causes the steam chamber to expand and spread laterally in the reservoir. High vertical permeability is crucial for the success of SAGD. The process performs better with bitumen and oils with low mobility, which is essential for the formation of a steam chamber, and not steam channels. SAGD has been more effective in Alberta than in California and Venezuela for the same reason.

Fig. 7 Steam Assisted Gravity Drainage (SAGD)

SAGD is highly energy intensive. Large volumes of water are required for steam generation, and the natural gas consumption for steam generation ranges between 200- 500 tonnes/sm³ of bitumen. There had been several attempts to improve the economics of SAGD. Notable examples among SAGD variations are VAPEX, ES-SAGD, and SAGP.

SAGD Variations

VAPEX is the non-thermal counterpart of SAGD, and it works on the same principles as SAGD. Instead of steam, a solvent gas, or a mixture of solvents, such as ethane, propane and butane is injected along with a carrier gas such as N₂ or CO₂. Solvent selection is based upon the reservoir pressure and temperature. The solvent gas is injected at its dew point. The carrier gas is intended to raise the dew point of the solvent vapour so that it remains in the vapour phase at the reservoir pressure. A vapour chamber is formed and it propagates laterally. The main mechanism is viscosity reduction. The process relies on molecular diffusion and mechanical dispersion for the transfer of solvent to the bitumen for viscosity reduction. Dispersion and diffusion are inherently slow, and therefore, are much less efficient than heat for viscosity reduction.

ES-SAGD

This process (Expanding Solvent SAGD) is another variation, where the addition of about 10% steam to the solvent mixture has been suggested to gain a 25% gain in the energy efficiency of VAPEX.

SAGP

Steam and Gas Push is also a variation, where a non-condensable gas such as natural gas or nitrogen, is injected with steam to reduce the high demand of steam in SAGD. These processes are in the early stages of development, and are not proven on a commercial scale.

Special Schemes

While screening guides are useful tools in selecting a suitable process for a given reservoir, it sometimes requires ingenuity in designing a recovery method for a problem reservoir. One such example is the Tangle flags reservoir on the Alberta- Saskatchewan border. The reservoir is sandstone, with 13 m thickness. Primary recovery was less than one percent due to severe water coning. Conventional steam flood was unsuitable for this viscous heavy oil reservoir because of the presence of bottom water and a gas cap. The special scheme designed for this reservoir consisted of vertical steam injectors and horizontal producers. The schematic is shown in Figure 8. The vertical wells are completed near the gas cap. Steam and condensed hot water mobilize the oil, which drains down, and is captured by the horizontal wells placed near the bottom of the reservoir. The positive downward pressure gradient minimized water coning. The process has been highly effective, and is currently operating with 11 pairs of wells.

Fig. 8 Tangle flags

2.1.4 In Situ Combustion:

In this method (Fig. 9), also known as fire flooding air or oxygen is injected to burn a portion (~10%) of the in-place oil to generate heat. Very high temperatures, in the range of 450-600°C, are generated in a narrow zone. High reduction in oil viscosity occurs near the combustion zone. The process has high thermal efficiency, since there is relatively small heat loss to the overburden or under burden, and no surface or wellbore heat loss. In some cases, additives such as water or a gas is used along with air, mainly to enhance heat recovery. Severe corrosion, toxic gas production and gravity override are common problems. *In situ* combustion has been tested in many places, however, very few projects have been economical and none has advanced to commercial scale.

The main variations of in situ combustion are:

- Forward combustion,
- Reverse combustion,
- High pressure air injection.

In forward combustion, ignition occurs near the injection well, and the hot zone moves in the direction of the air flow, whereas in reverse combustion, ignition occurs near the production well, and the heated zone moves in the direction counter to the air flow. Reverse combustion has not been successful in the field because of the consumption of oxygen in the air before it reaches the production well. High pressure air injection involves low temperature oxidation of the in-place oil. There is no ignition. The process is being tested in several light oil reservoirs in the USA.

Fig. 9 In situ Combustion

THAI and CAPRI Processes

THAI (Toe-To-Heel Air Injection) and CAPRI (variation of THAI with a catalyst for in situ upgrading) are two other variations of *in situ* combustion, proposed as economic alternatives of SAGD. These processes utilize a combination of a vertical well and a horizontal well (strategically placed to capture the mobilized oil), as opposed to a pair of horizontal wells for SAGD. The vertical well, placed near the top of the reservoir, is the injector; and the horizontal well, placed near the base of the reservoir, serves as the producer. Initially, steam is injected to establish communication between the injector and the producer. Compressed air from the atmosphere is injected subsequently to bring about ignition/slow oxidation. High temperatures brought on by ignition mobilize the heavy oil/tar sands, which flows from the toe to the heel of the horizontal well. In CAPRI process, it is proposed that the thermally cracked oil, captured by the horizontal well can be economically upgraded to lighter fractions by utilizing a catalytic sheath around the horizontal well. THAI and CAPRI (Fig. 10) are expected to have higher

thermal efficiency and less environmental impact. They have the potential to be applicable to a broader range of reservoirs, including thin formations of low pressure, deep reservoirs and reservoirs of poor quality. Recovery factors are estimated to be 70-80% OIP. Both processes are in the experimental phase and face several technical challenges to overcome.

Fig. 10 THAI & CAPRI Process

2.2 NON – THERMAL METHOD

Non-thermal methods are best suited for light oils (<100 cp). In a few cases, they are applicable to moderately viscous oils (<2000 cp), which are unsuitable for thermal methods. The two major objectives in non-thermal methods are:

- lowering the interfacial tension,
- improving the mobility ratio.

Most non-thermal methods require considerable laboratory studies for process selection and optimization. The three major classes under non-thermal methods are: miscible, chemical and immiscible gas injection methods (see Fig. 4). A number of miscible methods have been

commercially successful. A few chemical methods are also notable. Among immiscible gas drive processes, CO₂ immiscible method has been more successful than others.

2.2.1 Miscible Flooding:

Miscible flooding implies that the displacing fluid is miscible with the reservoir oil either at first contact (SCM) or after multiple contacts (MCM). A narrow transition zone (mixing zone) develops between the displacing fluid and the reservoir oil, inducing a piston-like displacement. The mixing zone and the solvent profile spread as the flood advances. The change in concentration profile of the displacing fluid with time is shown in Figure 11. Interfacial tension is reduced to zero in miscible flooding, therefore, $N_c = \infty$. Displacement efficiency approaches 1 if the mobility ratio is favourable ($M < 1$). The various miscible flooding methods include:

- miscible slug process,
- enriched gas drive,
- vaporizing gas drive,
- high pressure gas (CO₂ or N₂) injection.

Fig. 11 Miscible flooding (Change in concentration profile)

Miscible Slug Process

It is an SCM (single contact miscible) type process, where a solvent, such as propane or pentane, is injected in a slug form (4-5% HCPV). The miscible slug is driven using a gas such as methane or nitrogen, or water. This method is applicable to sandstone, carbonate or reef-type reservoirs, but is best suited for reef-type reservoirs. Gravity segregation is the inherent problem in miscible flooding. Viscous instabilities can be dominant, and displacement efficiency can be poor. Reef-type reservoirs can afford vertical gravity stabilized floods, which can give recoveries as high as 90% OOIP. Several such floods have been highly successful in Alberta, Canada. Availability of solvent and reservoir geology are the deciding factors in the feasibility of the process. Hydrate formation and asphaltene precipitation can be problematic.

Enriched Gas Drive

This is an MCM type process, and involves the continuous injection of a gas such as natural gas, flue gas or nitrogen, enriched with C₂-C₄ fractions. At moderately high pressures (8-12 MPa), these fractions condense into the reservoir oil and develop a transition zone. Miscibility is achieved after multiple contacts between the injected gas and the reservoir oil. Increase in oil phase volume and reduction in viscosity contrast can also be contributing mechanisms towards enhanced recovery. The process is limited to deep reservoirs (>6000 ft) because of the pressure requirement for miscibility.

Vaporizing Gas Drive

This also is an MCM type process, and involves the continuous injection of natural gas, flue gas or nitrogen under high pressure (10-15 Mpa). Under these conditions, the C₂-C₆ fractions are vaporized from the oil into the injected gas. A transition zone develops and miscibility is achieved after multiple contacts. A limiting condition is that the oil must have sufficiently high C₂-C₆ fractions to develop miscibility. Also, the injection pressure must be lower than the

reservoir saturation pressure to allow vaporization of the fractions. Applicability is limited to reservoirs that can withstand high pressures.

CO₂ Miscible

CO₂ Miscible method has been gaining prominence in recent years, partly due to the possibility of CO₂ sequestration. Apart from environmental objectives, CO₂ is a unique displacing agent, because it has relatively low minimum miscibility pressures (MMP) with a wide range of crude oils. CO₂ extracts heavier fractions (C₅-C₃₀) from the reservoir oil and develops miscibility after multiple contacts. The process is applicable to light and medium light oils (>30° API) in shallow reservoirs at low temperatures. CO₂ requirement is of the order of 500-1500 sm³/sm³ oil, depending on the reservoir and oil characteristics. Many injection schemes are in use for this method. Particularly notable among them is the WAG (Water Alternating Gas) process, where water and CO₂ are alternated in small slugs, until the required CO₂ slug size is reached (about 20% HCPV). This approach tends to reduce the viscous instabilities. Cost and availability and the necessary infrastructure of CO₂ are therefore major factors in the feasibility of the process. Asphaltene precipitation can be a problem in some cases. Currently there are 80 CO₂ floods in North America.

N₂ Miscible

This process is similar to CO₂ miscible process in principle and mechanisms involved to achieve miscibility, however, N₂ has high MMP with most reservoir oils. This method is applicable to light and medium light oils (>30° API), in deep reservoirs with moderate temperatures. Cantarell N₂ flood project in Mexico is the largest of its kind at present, and is currently producing about 500,000 B/D of incremental oil .

2.2.2 Chemical Flooding:

Chemical methods utilize a chemical formulation as the displacing fluid, which promotes a decrease in mobility ratio and/or an increase in the capillary number. Many commercial projects were in operation in the 1980's, among which, some were successful, but many were failures. The current chemical floods activity is low, except in China. The future holds promise because of the high demand for energy, and also because of the advancement in technology. Considerable experience and understanding have been gained from the past chemical floods projects. Economics is the major deterrent in the commercialization of chemical floods. It must also be noted that the technology does not exist currently for reservoirs of certain characteristics. The major chemical flood processes are polymer flooding, surfactant flooding, alkaline flooding, micellar flooding and ASP (alkali- surfactant-polymer) flooding (see *Fig. 4*). Other methods tested include emulsion, foam and the use of microbes, but their impact has not been significant on EOR production thus far.

Polymer Flooding

Water soluble polymers, such as polyacrylamides and poly- saccharides are effective in improving mobility ratio and reducing permeability contrast. In most cases, polymer flooding is applied as a slug process (20-40% PV) and is driven using dilute brine. Polymer concentration is between 200-2000 ppm. There were many polymer floods in the past, but recoveries were less than 10% in most cases. The major limitations include loss of polymer to the porous medium, polymer degradation and in some cases, loss of injectivity. One of the common reasons for the failure of polymer floods in the past was that it was applied too late in the waterflood, when the mobile oil saturation was low. The process will be more effective if applied earlier during a waterflood, at water breakthrough, for example, when the oil saturation is above the residual oil saturation.

Surfactant Flooding

Surfactants are effective in lowering interfacial tension between oil and water. Petroleum sulfonates or other commercial surfactants are often used. An aqueous surfactant slug is followed with a polymer slug, and the two chemical slugs are driven using brine. There were a number of surfactant floods in the past, but they were largely ineffective, mainly due to excessive surfactant loss to the porous medium. Surfactant adsorption and reactions with the rock minerals were severe in some cases. Treatment and disposal of emulsions were also of concern.

Alkaline Flooding

In alkaline flooding an aqueous solution of an alkaline chemical, such as hydroxide, carbonate or orthosilicate of sodium, is injected in a slug form. The alkaline chemical reacts with the acid components of the crude oil and produces the surfactant *in situ*. IFT reduction is the main mechanism. Spontaneous emulsification may also take place. Drop entrainment or drop entrapment may occur depending on the type of emulsion formed, which may enhance or diminish the recovery. Alkalis can cause changes in wettability, however, large concentrations are not successful for wettability alterations. Field results have been discouraging (RF 0-3% OIP). The process is complex to design due to the various reactions that take place between the alkaline chemical and the reservoir rock and fluids.

Micellar Flooding

Micellar flooding has been more successful in the field than other chemical flooding processes. The main components of this method are a microemulsion slug (also known as a micellar slug) and a polymer slug. These two slugs are driven using brine. Microemulsions are surfactant-stabilized, oil-water dispersions with small drop size distributions (10^{-4} to 10^{-6} mm). Microemulsions can be “miscible” with reservoir oil as well as water. The two chemical slugs are designed such that ultra-low IFT (10^{-2} mN/m or lower) and favourable mobility ratio prevails during the most part of the displacement. The process has been tested in 45 field projects, and

it has been proven that the method is successful in banking and producing the residual oil left after a waterflood. Recovery factors ranged between 35-50% OIP in field projects. However, economics were unattractive due to the high cost of chemicals, the requirement of small well spacing, the high initial expense and the considerable delay in response. Moreover, the geology and conditions in many candidate reservoirs (high salinity, temperature and clay content) are unsuitable for the application of micellar flooding. The process holds potential, and deserves to be re-evaluated under the current economic conditions. Scaling groups have been derived for micellar flooding, which is a valuable tool for laboratory evaluation to reduce the risk in the field application of the process.

ASP Flooding

Alkaline-Surfactant-Polymer flooding is relatively new and is being evaluated through laboratory investigations as well as field tests. The method utilizes mainly three chemical formulations – alkali, surfactant and polymer solutions. The chemical slugs may be injected in sequence or more likely, as a premixed single slug. The major mechanisms are IFT reduction and improvement in mobility ratio. Field results are encouraging (RF 25-30% OIP). The method is capable of banking and producing residual oil. The process holds potential, however, the mechanisms are not fully understood. Economics are marginal at best.

2.2.3 Other Methods:

A few other methods, including combination methods such as Surfactant-Steam, Steam-Foam, and Micellar-ASP, were also tested for EOR. Notable among them are Microbial method and Foam Flooding.

Microbial EOR (MEOR)

Microbial EOR has been researched since the 1960's. A few field tests have also been carried out in the USA and other countries. Microbes react with a carbon source, such as oil and produce surfactant, slimes (polymers), biomass and gases such as CH₄, CO₂, N₂ and H₂ as well as solvents and certain organic acids. Oil recovery mechanisms in microbial EOR are those of the classic chemical methods, which include IFT reduction, emulsification, wettability alteration, improved mobility ratio, selective plugging, viscosity reduction, oil swelling and increased reservoir pressure due to the formation of gases. Increase in permeability can result from the acids formed. Microbes can be indigenous or exogenous. Exogenous microbes must adapt to reservoir temperature, salinity and hardness. Nutrients, such as molasses or ammonium nitrate are supplied to stimulate microbial growth in the reservoir. The process has advanced since its inception, and is receiving renewed interest in recent years. Performance rating is pending due to insufficient field trials.

Foam Flooding

Foam has been evaluated as an EOR agent since the early 1960's. It is a complex non-Newtonian fluid with properties and characteristics governed by many variables. Foam is a dispersion of a liquid (containing surfactant) in a gas such as CO₂, air, N₂, steam or natural gas. Simultaneous injection of a gas and surfactant solution, or the injection of a gas into the porous medium containing a surfactant solution, generates foam in situ. Foam forms, breaks and re-forms in the pore throats as fluids advance in the porous medium. The presence of oil inhibits the formation of foam, and is therefore not effective in mobilizing residual oil. Mobility of foam is lower than that of gas or steam, and it acts as a viscous fluid. Foam has been used (with limited success), as a mobility control agent or blocking agent, with steam and CO₂ in some reservoirs.

CHAPTER 3

CASE STUDIES

Different EOR case studies would be reviewed, the list of these cases are as follows;

1. The San Andres project
2. Tupungato-Refugio project
3. Xinjaing project.

The history of individual projects before the start of EOR application and the suitability of the reservoir and operations to EOR would be evaluated. Next the treatment design and frequency are reviewed. The project results are then evaluated in terms of:

- Production rate increase compared to baseline,
- Decrease in water cut,
- Increase in cumulative recovery,
- Microbe effectiveness as measured by oil compositional changes indicated by viscosity testing.

Field description, treatment and evaluation

San Andres project

This reservoir located in Hockley County, Texas, USA was discovered in 1945, and solution gas drive was used for its production until water-flooding begun in 1967 with 355 barrels per acre foot, at a saturation of 70%. MEOR application begun in 1994 and the oil in place at that time was 239 bbls/ac-ft at an oil saturation of 41%. Line drive pattern was used for the waterflooding with a spacing of 25 acres. The current formation pressure was assessed as 1000 psi. The produced gas-oil ratio is 500 SCF/bbl.

The average horizontal permeability of 1.7 md indicates pore throat size that is way smaller than what the microbes can enter. Nonetheless, most of the oil is from the natural fractures that the microbes can easily enter. 115°F is the reservoir temperature and it's ideal for the growth of microbes. Producing at a water cut of 91%, the average production for each well is 14 BOPD.

Treatment: Treatments comprised of ten barrels of microbe filled water down the annulus. For the first treatment, all wells for this project were shut-in for 3 days, thereafter, during the subsequent treatments, they were shut-in overnight. The wells were treated for every 14 days for the first three months, then after that every 28 days.

Evaluation: The reservoir was stabilized on a consistent 6.5%/ year decline for three years before EOR was begun. The decline has flattened to 0.6%/year. The production of water on this property is mixed with fresh water and then introduced. Water produced is metered only by carrying out well tests and is not adequately precise to the point where a conclusion concerning water-cut reduction can be drawn. Over the past 19 months 17,000 barrels of incremental oil have been produced which is 7% over the baseline. The on-going oil production rate of 440 BOPD is ten percent over baseline. The cumulative incremental upsurge is projected to stretch to 15% at the time the project ends.

Viscosity for an example well was studied versus shear rate and versus temperature. The baseline sample showed that these microbes can alter the crude to a significant extent. The area under the shear rate curve is reduced by 73% and the oil is more Newtonian. The temperature curve is shifted to the left approximately 10°F. Five samples taken after the start of EOR indicate that the microbes are indeed effectively altering the crude in the reservoir.

At the end of its life the water flood would have left in place 205 bbls/ac-ft versus 199 with EOR. The saturation of the residual oil is estimated to drop from 35.0% under water flood to 34.1% with EOR, a 2.5% improvement.

Tupungato-refugio project

This field located in Tupungato County, Medoza, Argentina was found in 1930. In 1940, 1979 and 1986 the three wells in the project were completed in the Victor Oscuro formation. Production in the reservoir was through a combination of water drive, solution gas drive and water flood. In June 1994, EOR began in one of the wells and by March 1995 it started in the two other wells. The original oil in place was 625 bbls/ac-ft with an oil saturation of 47% and gas saturation of 10% and average horizontal permeability of 0.8 mD. The wells are about 42 acres spaced and four spot pattern was used for water flooding. Fluid and rock characteristics favour microbe colonization. Completion methods for the wells are by open hole or slotted liner. The average production for each well is within the range of 90 BOPD, with a water cut of about 63%.

Treatment: The reservoir was initially treated with about 150 barrels of microbe-laden water, and then a 48 hour shut-in period was performed on 2 wells and for the other well it was 24 hours. The treatments that followed were 50 barrels every 15 days on two wells and every 30 days for the other well.

Evaluation: The project was on 7.1%/year decline for 29 months before EOR was begun. For the past 14 months, from the time when EOR began, the oil production rate has improved at a rate of 7.3%/ year. Also since the start of EOR, water production has increased, but the water cut decreased from 63.5% to 62%. More data is needed to reach a conclusion regarding the rate of increase versus cumulative production. Over the past 14 months, incremental oil of about 19,000 barrels has been produced which is 19% above the baseline. Oil production is 270 barrels per day, 29% percent over baseline. The projected cumulative incremental increase is about 57% by the end of the life of the project.

Viscosity for an example project well was studied versus shear rate and versus temperature. The baseline sample showed microbes could modify the crude significantly. The area under the shear rate curve is reduced by 54% and the oil is more Newtonian. The temperature curve is shifted to

the left approximately 10°F. The sample taken after the start of MEOR indicates the microbes are effectively altering the crude down hole. Oil in place at the end of the project life would have been 509 bbls/ac-ft versus 442 with EOR. Residual oil saturation is estimated to fall from 38.3% under water flood to 33.3% with EOR, a 13% improvement.

Xinjiang project

This field is located in No.1 Plant, Xinjiang Uygur Autonomous Region, P. R China situated in the Xinjiang Petroleum Administration Bureau. Solution gas drive was the primary drive mechanism here, although most of the wells are in the later stages of water flooding and are dispersed and not in the same reservoir. So production data can be evaluated but the reservoir performance can't be ascertained for this grouping. EOR application began in January 1995. Rod pumps were used for the wells and the pumps were set from 200 up to 6,000 feet above perforation for one well. Fluid and reservoir parameters all favour microbial growth.

Treatment: Every well was treated thrice. The initial treatment comprised of 150 barrels of microbe-filled liquid on 7 wells then 80 barrels on 3 wells, after that, 0-150 barrels of displacing water followed. The distance the rod pump was established above the perforations, then the pumping fluid level was used to calculate the displacement. The second and third treatments comprised 50 barrels for 6 wells and then 75 barrels for the further 4 wells with displacement water within the range of 0-70 barrels.

Evaluation: The wells in the project were on a rapid decline for the 24 months before EOR was begun. For the 6 months after the start of MEOR, the rate of oil production improved and then sustained a rate of about 300 barrels per day. Production of water declined once EOR began, the water cut decreased from 64% to 54%. And the trend in water cut against cumulative oil production which was growing quickly is now flat. Over the 6 months 14,000 barrels of incremental oil have been produced which is 43% over the baseline. Oil production is 300 barrels per day, 36% percent over baseline.

Viscosity for an example project well was studied versus shear rate and versus temperature. The baseline illustration showed microbes could modify the crude significantly. The area under the shear rate curve is reduced by 49%. The temperature curve is shifted to the left approximately 10°F. Due to the short duration of the microbe treating and the location of the project, viscosity curves are not available for the field treated oil. However, on five of the wells, the operator calculated an average reduction in viscosity at (49%) and an increase in gravity from 28.70 to 29.60 API (3.1%). Microbes positively improved the crude oil in this reservoir.

Comparisons between the projects

Similarities between the EOR projects

- The crude oil found in these reservoirs had high viscosity within the range of (4.5-50 cp).
- They all had solution gas drive as their primary drive mechanisms although the Tupungato-Refugio case was a combination of water drive and solution gas drive as its primary drive system.
- They all had reservoir depth within the range of (4745-5700) ft.
- They all had reservoir temperature within the range of (110- 160)°F.
- Before EOR application, they all had a high water-cut percentage.
- All the projects were initially placed on water flooding as a secondary recovery method. EOR was introduced as a tertiary recovery method.

Differences between the EOR projects

- The flood patterns were different for all of them, because of the differences in permeability.
- The treatment volume and shut in period for each case were different because they were developed to suit the indigenous reservoirs and were driven by specific models for the individual project.

- Rod pumps (artificial lift methods) were only used in the XINJIANG Project wells, probably due to higher viscosity and water-cut.
 - Each EOR project has different number of wells, and it's listed below.
1. The San Andres Project consists of 30 producer and 15 injection wells.
 2. The Tupungato-Refugio project consists of 3 producer wells.
 3. The Xinjiang project consists of 10 producer wells (Tables 2-4).

Analysing the Oil Production Result for the Three Projects

Projects	San Andres	Tupungato-Refugio	Xinjiang
Lithology	Fractured dolomite	Fractured sandstone	Sandstone
Depth (ft)	4745	5700	4900
Net Thickness (ft)	46	60	40
Porosity (fraction)	0.079	0.18	N/A
Effective Permeability [Range] (mD)	1.7 [0.10-10.0]	300 [150-1500]	70 [0.2-440]
Reservoir Temperature (°F)	115	160	110
Oil Density (°API)	29	28	29
Dead Oil Viscosity (cp)	4.5	9	50
Water salinity (mg/l cl)	40,000	42,000	8000
S _o at MEOR start (%)	41	47	N/A
Water cut (%)	91	63.5	64
Drive Mechanism	Solution gas	Solution gas and water drive	Solution gas
Flood pattern	Line drive	Four spot	N/A

Table 2: Comparing some of the characteristics of the three cases

S/N	Subject description	San Andreas project	Tupungato-Refugio project	Xianjiang project
1	Percentage decline	Was initially on a 6.5%/year decline, but after MEOR began, it flattened to 0.6%/year.	Was initially on a 7.1%/year decline, but for the past 14 months since the start of MEOR, it has inclined at the rate of 7.3%/year.	Was initially on a rapid decline for 24 months before MEOR began, but 6 months after the start of MEOR, oil production rate improved and then sustained a rate of about 300 barrels per day.
2	Oil Production Rate	Oil production increased by 10% or 40 BOPD after 19 months of microbe treating.	Oil production increased by 29% or 60 BOPD after 14 months of treating.	Oil production increased by 36% or 80 BOPD 6 months after treating.
3	Baseline Production	Current oil production of 440 BOPD is ten percent over baseline.	Current oil production of 270 BOPD is 29% percent over baseline.	Current oil production of 300 BOPD is 36% percent over baseline.
4	Incremental Production	Over the past 19 months 17,000 barrels of incremental oil have been produced which is 7% over the baseline	. Over the past 14 months, incremental oil of about 19,000 barrels has been produced which is 19% above the baseline	. Over the 6 months 14,000 barrels of incremental oil have been produced which is 43% over the baseline
5	Additional Field Wide Production Rate after Waterflooding	At the end of its life the waterflood would have left in place 205 bbls/ac-ft versus 199 with MEOR	Oil in place at the end of the project life would have been 509 bbls/ac-ft after waterflood versus 442 with MEOR	N/A
6	Effect on Residual Oil Saturation	The saturation of the residual oil is estimated to drop from 35.0% under waterflood to 34.1% with MEOR, a 2.5% improvement.	Residual oil saturation is estimated to fall from 38.3% under waterflood to 33.3% with MEOR, a 13% improvement	N/A

Table 3: Comparing oil production data between the three EOR cases

S/N	Subject description	San Andres project	Tupungato-Refugio project	Xinjiang project
1	Decrease in Water Cut	N/A	the water cut decreased from 63.5% to 62%	the water cut decreased from 64% to 54%
2	Water Production	N/A	Water production increased	Water production decreased

Table 4: Comparing water-cut and water production data between the projects

Analysing the Xinjiang projects success

Now we have to look at some of the reasons why EOR was so successful in the Xinjiang Project;

- It had a significantly higher viscosity (50 cp), compared to the other two projects (4.5 cp and 9 cp respectively), hence, creating room for the microbes to better alter the crude oil, thereby leading to a more gigantic improvement in oil production.
- Microbes don't thrive well under high temperature, so having the lowest temperature amongst the three cases apparently favoured the well-being of the microbes in the reservoir.
- The water salinity for this project was significantly lower than that of the others and without a shred of doubt, we can say this tremendously boosted the effectiveness of microbes in this reservoir compared to the others.
- The introduction of displacing water after Microbial water flooding seemed to be very effective too.
- Microbes are known to fare better in sandstone formations. The use of Rod pumps might have also bolstered the production rate.

CHAPTER 4

EOR CHALLENGES

4.1 Mature Oil Fields

Indonesia has more than 650 oil fields. These are a huge oil resources involves onshore and offshore locations. Pertamina Exploration and Production (E&P) is the national oil company which has the largest number of fields in Indonesia. The total number of fields had been covered 124 producing fields and 59 non active fields. These fields are spreading from North Sumatra to Papua. In general, these oil fields are mature field's categories (95% of total field). The oil production has been declined between 5-20% per year since several year ago. Many of their fields are in depleted pressure condition. Almost of the reservoir pressure below the bubble point (pb). Due to mature fields, a lot of the oil wells had high water cuts and it has caused non active Fields. These mature fields were discovered since 40 years ago. Its fields usually have lack of data, old Facilities, depleted pressure, low reserve, high water cut, missing production data, limited core data, and logging data.

4.2 Huge Initial Capital Investment

The extra investments are being spent to develop new EOR facilities and to rejuvenate the production infrastructure. These activities are requiring huge capital expenditure (capex) and operational expenditure (opex). From laboratory work to field implementation of an eor project requires long time. Thus, after implementation, production response does not occur immediately. During that time, the oil company should spend a lot of much money and effort. In fact, Duri Field used steam flooding was approximately 9 years (1985-1994) to achieve peak production late in the year 1994.

4.3 Chemical Import Dependence

Cost is the main factor in business. For example, the chemical injection required high costs in Minas Field. The total cost was approximately \$110 for 1.0 barrel of oil. This cost consisted of \$30 for polymer, \$70 for surfactant, and \$10 for facilities. Nowadays, chemical import is the

main factor to increase eor costs. Many oil fields are suitable by chemical injections in Pertamina Exploration and Production. SKKMigas predicted the total amount of chemicals are requiring for eor approximately 8 million tons .

4.4 Oil Price Effects

The EOR activities depend on oil price, royalty, and tax advantages[20]. In fact, based on depth and oil gravity are being considered, almost 80% of the reservoir in the world are favourable by CO₂ injection. The decisions on the future eor will not only be based on depth and oil gravity criteria, but oil price as well, which is important. Obviously, the economy is playing a role in whether eor projects move on or not. In general, eor activity is increasing when the oil prices increase and vice versa. For example, in the early 1980s when oil prices were up to \$50/bbl, the eor activity increased also. But, the impact of a lower oil price of EOR activity has fallen in 1994. At that time, the oil price was below \$20 /bbl. Commonly, the Indonesian Crude Oil Price (ICP) has increased from 2001 to 2013. However, the oil price has dropped below \$60/bbl since late 2014 . Therefore, eor activities will be worse in the near future if the oil price continue to fall. The oil price influence the petroleum industry activities. The lower oil price will reduce several activities such as research, developing budgets, capital spending, employment pattern, and exploration.

4.5 Lack of EOR Experts

EOR method is quite complicated in field scale. This phenomenon is dissimilar between in laboratory and in the field scales. Then, to solve the complicated problems it requires expert skill. Currently, inexpert skills in EOR design and implementation have become one of major problems in Indonesia. Numerous experts are working in multinational oil company in overseas. Its phenomenon due to the high gap in the salary between Indonesia and overseas. Finally, lack of expert skills will be a barrier for developing and implementing EOR in the future.

CHAPTER 5

CURRENT STATUS OF EOR

Most of the EOR activity took place in the USA in the past, and the bulk of the production came from that country. Figure 12 shows the EOR production in EOR projects world-wide (specially USA). The total EOR production in USA is declining . The major contributor was thermal methods, and that is also on the decline, mainly because most attractive reservoirs have already been exploited. Production from gas injection is increasing, and that is mainly due to CO₂ floods. Production from chemical floods is non-existent at present. The total EOR production in the USA today constitutes about 12% of the total domestic oil production.

Fig. 12 EOR Production Worldwide

The total world oil production today (including condensate and natural gas liquids) is 84.5 million B/D. EOR production worldwide is about 2.5×10^6 B/D, and almost all of it comes from USA, Mexico, Venezuela, Canada, Indonesia and China, as seen in Figure 13. Figure 14 shows the breakdown of the production from the contributing countries. Thermal methods are dominant in five countries. Chemical floods are active in China, the total production being 200,000 B/D in 2006.

Recent advancements in technology and the current economic climate have resulted in a renewed interest in EOR. Future growth of EOR will depend on both technology and oil price. Long term commitments in capital and human resources, as well as in R&D, are essential for success in EOR practice. While EOR screening methods are useful tools, recovery methods that are considered unattractive in most reservoirs can be applicable in specific situations. Also, proven EOR methods may be adapted to adverse conditions, as experienced in Canada. Considering the widening gap between demand and supply of energy, EOR will continue to play a significant role in improving recovery factors.

Fig. 13 Current EOR production from contributing countries (Percentages are those of the total EOR production of 2.5 million B/D.)

Fig. 14 Major EOR projects & production worldwide

CHAPTER 6

CONCLUSION

Crude oil recovery takes place in three production stages primary, secondary and tertiary oil recovery processes. On average, oil recovery from the primary and secondary production stages is approximately one-third of the original oil-in-place (OOIP), while the remaining two-thirds of the oil, can be partially recovered through the application of tertiary processes also known as enhanced oil recovery (EOR) processes, which are key drivers for incremental oil recovery. EOR processes include thermal (TEOR), chemical (CEOR), gas flooding miscible and immiscible (GEOR) and microbial or MEOR processes.

- Thermal EOR techniques are applied for the recovery of heavy oils. In particular, steam flooding is the dominant thermal EOR technique worldwide. Increase in oil productivity is achieved through viscosity reduction, oil swelling, steam stripping and thermal cracking.
- Among the many EOR methods tested, only a few have been commercially successful.
- Steam injection based recovery methods, such as CSS and steam flooding have been highly successful for heavy oils and tar sands.
- Miscible CO₂ flooding has had considerable success for light oils, although economics are not clear at this stage.

- Chemical EOR techniques are suitable for application in mature oil fields. Globally, oil recovery using CEOR techniques have remained insignificant since the 1990s with the exception of China. Among the CEOR techniques, polymer/surfactant flooding through IFT reduction between the displacing liquid (i.e. water) and oil has the best potential for ultimate oil recovery. However, polymer flooding is less complex and the most widely deployed technique for mobility control.
- Miscible and immiscible gas injection or GEOR are suitable for application in light, condensate and volatile oil reservoirs. CO₂ is considered the most widely used gas for GEOR injection especially in the US Permian Basin, where most of the CO₂ field projects have been deployed. In the US, continuous growth of CO₂ flooding projects is expected. N₂ and hydrocarbon gas injection projects have been deployed in Canada and the US, although incremental oil recovery from these processes has been negligible.
- MEOR is a promising and eco-friendly recovery process with potential for future incremental oil recovery. The main downsides of MEOR are longer time intervals are required to attain incremental oil production and MEOR renders the lowest oil recovery in a given period in comparison to other EOR techniques.

Huge potentials for incremental oil recovery exist through the application of EOR processes; however, the volume of recoverable oil is greatly dependent on the implemented EOR technique. Among the key EOR techniques deployed in oil fields, miscible gas injection EOR and thermal EOR processes are currently the most commonly used techniques in the field. Continuous evolution of EOR processes in the near future should take a synergistic approach from different EOR technologies.

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